

Challenges of Introducing Human Rights Education in the African Countries, and Proposing a Contextual Human Rights Education Course for the African Universities through the Lens of Socioecoethical model of Human Rights Education

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Profile

Dr. Munir Moosa Sadruddin is a human rights educator, social anthropologist, and socio-educational theorist. He holds a Ph.D. in Education with a concentration in Human Rights Education. He has been working as an Assistant Professor of Education at SMI University, Pakistan for more than nine years. He is also a founding volunteer director of Global Forum for Teacher Educators, where he offers complementary human rights education to children and women of marginalized communities.

Munir holds an esteemed international standing. He is the recipient of the Presidency of Turks and Related Communities (YTB) Research Fellowship, the Commonwealth UK, Distance Education Scholarship, and has served as a Visiting Academic Scholar at the Humboldt University of Berlin, and the University of California, Berkeley. He has also delivered guest lectures at global institutes (face-to-face and online) including the School of Education, UC Berkeley, Adult School Berkeley, and the Leuphana University of Lüneburg, Germany.

He has developed a series of socio-eco-ethical models, including socioecoethical model of human rights education, socioecoethical model of social work, and socio-ethical model of inclusivity, with global application in human rights education, social work, and inclusivity. He is using radically alternative approaches to break the prejudices and social constructs of academia through open educational praxis.

You can learn more about him at <https://sites.google.com/view/munir-moosa-sadruddin>

Professor Dr. Muyiwa Falaiye, Ph.D, MNAL is a Professor of African Socio-Political Philosophy and an expert in African and Diaspora Studies. With over 60 publications in high impact local and international journals, and frontline peer-reviewed books, Falaiye has, through his research and teaching activities, demonstrated competence in Identity and African Diaspora Studies, African Philosophy and Philosophy of Development. His commitment to transformative research has earned him awards and commendations, including: the prestigious Fellowship at the Centre for African Studies, University of Florida, Gainesville, USA and several African Studies Travel Grants. He has leadership hands-on-experiences in coordinating interdisciplinary and collaborative researches. At different times, he has served as member of the Board of several journals and book series, including the African Social Studies Series published by E.J. Brill, Netherlands. Currently, he is Dean of the Faculty of Arts, University of Lagos and the Director of the collaborative research Institute between the University of Lagos and the University of the West Indies – Institute of African and Diaspora Studies (IADS).

Professor Falaiye is a Member of Philosophical Association of Nigeria, African Studies Association of U.S.A, UK, Italy, Russia, Nigerian Academy of Letters and a Fellow of the African Studies Center, Leiden, Netherlands.

Background

Africa is the world's second most populated, and the largest continent, spread out in over fifty-four¹ sovereign countries. The combined population of the African continent is around 1.39 billion, of which, women constitute more than half the population (The United Nations, 2022, as cited in Worldometer, 2022a).

Africa is divided into five sub-regions² namely Northern Africa³, Western Africa, Middle Africa, Eastern Africa⁴, and Southern Africa⁵. The continent is often grouped into North Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa. North Africa⁶, also referred to as Saharan Africa comprises seven modern countries. This part is conceptually connected with Asia, the Middle East, and the Islamic World. Whereas, Sub-Saharan Africa comprises forty-six⁷ to forty-eight⁸ countries of four regions.

According to documentation from the United Nations (2019, as cited in the World Bank, 2020), the total population of Sub-Saharan Africa stands at approximately 1.136 billion. In contrast, Northern Africa's recent population is reported as 253 million (Worldometer, 2022b). Notably, Nigeria retains its position as the most populous country in the West African region, while Algeria holds the distinction of being the largest sovereign state by area in North Africa.

European Colonialism and Imperialism are the distinctive features of Africa's history⁹. Today, it is one of the progressive constitutional democracies in the world, with a diverse cultural heritage¹⁰.

African human rights (HR) landscape portrays struggles, complexities, and vulnerabilities. HR violations in a good number of African states are among the highest in the world¹¹. In the context of human rights conditions, a pertinent question arises: why, despite the existence of regional laws and global commitments, are human rights not fully integrated and realized in practical implementation? One of the reasons could be “the growing gap between the AU [African Union] political organs and African human rights institutions” (Nantulya, 2021). Furthermore, the compromised state of human rights in many African countries is attributed to a combination of factors, including ideological, cultural, and traditional barriers; a deficiency in understanding the human rights system; the imposition of repressive policies; inadequate justice and accountability mechanisms; and a lack of attention to the diverse ethnic composition within these nations (European Union, 2013; Senyonjo, 2018).

¹ <https://www.worldatlas.com/articles/how-many-countries-are-in-africa.html>

² <https://www.worldatlas.com/geography/regions-of-africa.html#:~:text=The%20United%20Nations%20Geoscheme%20divides,Southern%20Africa%20is%20the%20smallest.>

³ Largest sub-region by land area

⁴ Most populated region

⁵ Smallest sub-region by land area and least populated

⁶ Several dimensions of contemporary North Africa, such as the great influence of the Arab culture and Islam make it a unique and non-comparable region from the south.

⁷ According to the UNDP

⁸ As claimed by the World Bank

⁹ See <https://en.unesco.org/general-history-africa>

¹⁰ Often referred to as triple heritage, namely Indigenous/Traditional, Islamic, and the Western

¹¹ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1256220/highest-human-rights-and-rule-of-law-index-by-country/>

The researchers view Human Rights Education (HRE) as the panacea to HR violations in the African continent. But are African countries a proponent of HRE? What is the scope, and the current state of HRE across Africa? It is crucial to unfold these questions to comprehend the contribution of HRE towards inculcating HR values, to identify the gaps in policies and practices, and to propose measures for bridging the gaps.

This study is designed to comprehend the state of HR and HRE, along with the barriers to introducing HRE in Africa. It also proposes an HRE course for African university learners.

Objectives

1. Comprehend the state of HR and HRE in Africa
2. Identify the challenges of introducing HRE in Africa
3. Propose a contextual HRE course under socioethical model of HRE.

Research Design

We have used systematic literature review (SLR) and learning design (LD) model as research approaches.

Utilizing a robust methodology, SLR discerns all relevant empirical evidence aligned with predefined inclusion criteria to address a specific research query (Davis et al., 2014). Our approach involved conducting a comprehensive desk review aimed at comprehending the historical context, current landscape of HR and HRE, as well as the challenges entailed in integrating HRE across the broader African context. Employing a meticulously designed search protocol and identifying key terminologies, we conducted thorough searches across prominent databases, imposing no limitations on publication dates. Data compilation followed the Problem, Interventions, Comparison, and Outcomes (PICO) chart methodology, while the inclusion or exclusion of studies adhered to the PRISMA Flowchart guidelines. The findings stemming from the desk review furnish certain insights; however, it's important to note that several pertinent studies within this purview remain undocumented. Moreover, the available literature falls short of providing a definitive portrayal of the HR and HRE landscape in Africa, attributed to contextual nuances and methodological constraints.

LD is “a methodology for enabling teachers/designers to make more informed decisions on how they go about designing learning activities and interventions, which is pedagogically informed and makes effective use of appropriate resources and technologies. This includes the design of resources and individual learning activities right up to curriculum-level design” (Conole, 2013, p. 8). We first adapted ADDIE (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation) model¹³ with the inclusion of ‘S’- Scoping Review, and exclusion of ‘I’ and ‘E’. We termed our model as SADD (Scoping Review, Analysis, Design, and Development). We also reflected on the model proposed by Narcisa (2014) as a supplementary resource.

Initiating a successful course design process entails a thorough assessment of the sociocultural and political context of a nation, the prevailing educational landscape,

¹³ An instructional design approach used to develop teaching/learning resources, training courses, and modules.

pertinent policies, existing educational demands, and the alignment and receptiveness of the country to educational reform. Ahmed et al. (2020) suggested, “A critical approach to HRE, therefore, must recognize and examine the underlying ideologies or frames of reference that influence choice among priorities and the resolution of conflicts that inevitably come up with the introduction of value-laden HRE” (pp.197-198).

Drawing from practical expertise in the field, our approach commenced with a comprehensive analysis of data derived from the desk review. This initial phase enabled the identification of gaps and key determinants crucial for the effective development of a course. Subsequently, a systematic exploration of existing HRE courses, tailored for university-level instruction, was conducted. This involved deliberating on overarching objectives, devising optimal teaching strategies and methodologies, establishing a coherent structure, and curating an array of learning resources. The culmination of these efforts materialized in the formulation of a comprehensive course framework. Continuing in this trajectory, an in-depth exploration and dialogue were undertaken to address multifaceted facets of HRE course design. By delineating precise learning objectives, refining these objectives, and meticulously shaping a contextual course outline specific to the African setting, a coherent and relevant curriculum framework emerged. Parallely, a diverse array of resources and learning activities were meticulously gathered from diverse sources, enriching the educational content.

We recognize the significance of the Implementation and Evaluation phases, but due to scope limitations, we did not consider these stages. We propose ‘SADDI-RAR’ (Scoping Review, Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Reflective Action Research Cycle) as a future model. In the future, there is a plan to execute face-to-face surveys and convene focus groups, aimed at pinpointing existing gaps in HR knowledge. This approach will also delve into unraveling challenges and requisites for introducing the HRE course, as perceived by university students and educators. Additionally, the implementation of a pilot study is envisioned, which would serve to enhance the validation of the course outline, ensuring its effectiveness on a broader scale.

Brief History Human Rights in Africa

There is a close association between HR discourse¹⁴ and Africa’s independence movement. The people of Africa have suffered from years of slavery, apartheid, and imperialism. Denial of human and civil rights laid the foundation of anti-colonialism.

Nationalism and pan-Africanism movements, followed by African socialism, the Organization of African Unity, and the African Union (AU) are credited for establishing and preserving the HR system in the African continent.

The history of HR in the African continent comprises a multitude of narratives, encompassing various periods from political and ideological perspectives. These periods include pre-colonial, colonial, post-colonial, and contemporary eras.

¹⁴ For information about historical milestone of human rights in the world, please refer to <https://cdn1.sph.harvard.edu/wp-content/uploads/sites/134/2016/07/Human-Rights-A-brief-intro-2016.pdf>

During pre-colonialism,¹⁵ the customary ethnic communities were living under the traditional African political systems. Cultural and linguistic homogeneity unified pre-colonial societies. Individual-conscious justice systems were prevalent. Mutua (1995) narrated, “A brief examination of the norms governing legal, political, and social structures in pre-colonial societies demonstrates that the concept of rights... informed the notion of justice and supported a measure of individualism” (p.2). Although HR was not pronounced in legal documents, individual rights were embedded in the culture and religion and practiced across the communities (Collins, 2001). Much work is not chronicled about the state of HR during the pre-colonial era. However, Mutua (1995) mentioned, “African pre-colonial past was neither idyllic nor free of the abuses of power and authority common to all human societies” (p.1).

Africa witnessed the most incongruous socio-political and economic transformation during colonialism¹⁶. During this period, a prevailing sense of hegemony and stringent regulations characterized the landscape. The majority of African states underwent colonization by Western European powers within the timeframe of 1881 to 1914. This colonial era introduced European legal and cultural frameworks that often clashed with traditional values (EI-Obaid & Appiagyei-Atua, 1996). During this period, individuals endured the most severe manifestations of human rights abuses, facing the denial of fundamental social, civil, and political rights. Gutto (1991) endorsed, “In human rights terms colonialism was a negation of human rights and democratic organization and governance of society. Not only did it deny and violate specific rights, but it also created a culture of authoritarianism in politics and it created economies tied in unequal and subordinate relations within the global capitalist system” (p.11). The colonial power nurtured educated leaders who propagated the concept of self-determination, consequently catalyzing the movement for African nationalism.

The post-colonial trajectory is etched with profound disillusionment and lingering resentment. The establishment of international HR frameworks and regional policies ushered in a new era of HR awareness in Africa. Yet, the underlying issues of fundamental rights remained entrenched, influenced by power dynamics. As the transition from European dominance to national independence unfolded, numerous states grappled with HR abuses precipitated by political upheaval, underdevelopment, and cultural clashes. During this juncture, a spectrum of ideologies surfaced, encompassing socialism, one-partyism, pro-Americanism, pan-Arabism, and pan-Africanism (EI-Obaid & Appiagyei-Atua, 1996). Today, HR serves to establish “a powerful perspective relating to the present and past collective experiences of injustice, exclusion, and domination within global politics” (Thoba, 2017, p.1). But the powerful states look at HR as a strategic tool to legitimize political change and dominate other African states.

Contemporary Africa¹⁷ is the kaleidoscope of ethnic diversity, socio-economic development, cultural practices, political beliefs, and orientations. Many African states have passed legal HR documents and ratified global commitments, yet experiencing

¹⁵ For more information, read <https://www.jstor.org/stable/43658228>

¹⁶ For more information, read

https://www.tralac.org/images/News/Documents/Analysis_of_Colonialism_and_Its_Impact_in_Africa_Ocheni_and_Nwankwo_CSCa_nada_2012.pdf

¹⁷ For more information, read <https://www.scielo.br/j/sant/a/ZTmV4k4tPtpZLJGc6DWXfmH/?lang=en&format=pdf>

complex HR issues like religious intolerance, poverty influx, and inter-ethnic atrocities (Schraeder, 2020). Oloka-Onyango (2000) articulated, “The human rights situation on the African continent today is most certainly in a state of considerable flux. At the same time, Africa remains a continent marginalized from the tremendous technological, economic and developmental achievements that the world has made over the last few decades” (p.2).

Overall, the history of African HR is pickled with complex and multi-layered ideologies.

Regions of Contemporary Africa¹⁸

Laws and Policies on Human Rights

There are various schools of thought regarding the establishment of the HR system in Africa. The influence of significant documents like the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) and the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights on HR provisions in Africa is widely acknowledged. However, it's worth noting that among African communities, there exists a prevailing belief that inherent rights have been inherent since the emergence of early humans on African soil. This viewpoint is rooted in the assertion that traditions were cultivated and achievements were made, alongside

¹⁸ <https://www.rienner.com/uploads/5ee8ecb9665f6.pdf>

enduring struggles for HR, although many of these endeavors remain unrecorded. The Law of Lagos¹⁹, and constitutions of Namibia and South Africa are also believed to have instituted a national HR mechanism in Africa.

The constitutions of most independent African countries are modeled on the pattern of UDHR. However, there are socio-cultural, political, and ideological reservations to its domestic implementation (Mbaku, 2020; Viljoen, 2012). Motala (1989) narrated, “Much of the present philosophical and ideological tenets of human rights, which are reflected or interpreted in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, are a product of a particular social order and thus reflect a particular ideology. Traditional African societies had their own conceptions of human rights” (p.373). Ibhawoh (2020) described that the International HR documents overlooked the historical tensions in the meanings and ordering of rights. Agbor (2020) expressed, “The view that international human rights are a product of European civilization is not only fallacious and misleading but untenable and does not accord with the plethora of incontrovertible evidence that exists... their claim that they are the proprietors and progenitors of human rights is not only fallacious and ludicrous but also vitiates the credibility and intent of the entire movement” (p.10). In short, African countries adopt UDHR-based constitutions, yet implementation faces socio-cultural and ideological challenges, and scholars debate how UDHR fits African traditions while countering claims of exclusive European origins.

Significantly, during colonial rule, African leaders were often marginalized from initial discussions on crafting universal HR documents, leading historians to heavily depend on Western archives for documenting HR history. Ibhawoh argued “In human rights historiography, the vocabulary of human rights remains inextricably linked with possessive individualism, operating as the ideological groundwork for the rise of capitalism and mass democracy. This interpretation of universal human rights is framed as paradigmatic. However, in the age of empire, interpretations of human rights centered primarily on the collective rights of people appealed more to those living under colonial domination than a notion of human rights premised on narrow possessive individualism. In Africa, nationalists and anti-colonial activists articulated an alternate vision of human rights that prioritized the collective rights of people to self-determination over atomized individual liberties. The relationship between self-determination within anti-colonialism and individual-centered human rights was not simply one of succession or displacement; it was also one of contestation and repudiation” (2020, p.40). Similarly, EI-Obaid and Appiagyei-Atua expressed that the HR perspective in Africa is “neither entirely individualistic nor purely communal” (1996, p.819).

In 1963, the Charter of the Organisation of African Unity (OAU)²⁰ was established to fight decolonization, racial discrimination, and for practicing HR. However, it weighed socio-economic development and state sovereignty over HR protection. In 1981, after a long hostility by some African states, the African [Banjul] Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (ACHPR)²¹ was passed. It was the first regional HR instrument that formalized the African HR system.

¹⁹ <https://www.icj.org/conferencia-africana-sobre-el-imperio-de-la-ley-lagos-nigeria-3-7-de-enero-de-1961-informe-sobre-los-trabajos-de-la-conferencia/>

²⁰ <https://www.refworld.org/docid/3ae6b36024.html>

²¹ <https://treaties.un.org/doc/Publication/UNTS/Volume%201520/volume-1520-I-26363-English.pdf>

Later, the African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights was established in 1987 to promote and protect HR, and to implement the ACHPR, but it was not executed with zeal because of clawback clauses. Mutua (2000) expressed that the normative weaknesses in the Charter created an "ineffectual enforcement system [and] general impotence of its implementing body, the African Commission" (p.6).

In 1990, the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child was adopted²². To further strengthen the HR protection system, and to ensure compliance with local and international HR laws and treaties, OAU adopted the protocol for the establishment of the African Court on Human and Peoples Rights (AfCHPR)²³ in 1998²⁴. To deepen Africa's commitment to social, economic, and cultural rights, the members of the OAU passed The Constitutive Act of the African Union in 2001²⁵ and established the African Union (AU) on July 9, 2002. AU has been instrumental in catalyzing HR development and eradicating all forms of colonialism. It passed and agreed with three important instruments namely A declaration formulating new Principles Governing Democratic Elections in Africa, 2002; A declaration on Democracy, [and] Political, Economic and Corporate Governance in Africa, 2002, and African Union Convent on Preventing and Combating Corruption, 2003. Since its establishment, some regional HR institutes have also emerged, for example, the Pan African Parliament, the Peace, and Security Council, the Economic, Social, and Cultural Council, and the African Peer Review Mechanism of the New Partnership for Africa's Development (NEPAD)²⁶.

In 2003, the Protocol on the Rights of Women in Africa (Maputo Protocol)²⁷ was adopted to recognize women's empowerment. In 2006, the African Youth Charter²⁸, in 2007 the African Charter on Democracy, Elections, and Governance²⁹, and in 2009, the African Union Convention for the Protection and Assistance of Internally Displaced Persons was adopted³⁰ (Centre for Human Rights, 2016). Since then, African countries have framed a good number of HR laws and policies.

Thus, the African continent utilizes HR safeguarding via local, regional, and international frameworks, yet the reporting on their implementation and resultant outcomes remains incomplete.

²² https://au.int/sites/default/files/treaties/36804-treaty-african_charter_on_rights_welfare_of_the_child.pdf

²³ https://au.int/sites/default/files/treaties/36393-treaty-0019_-_protocol_to_the_african_charter_on_human_and_peoplesrights_on_the_establishment_of_an_african_court_on_human_and_peoples_rights_e.pdf

²⁴ It started procedures in late 2006

²⁵ https://au.int/sites/default/files/pages/34873-file-constitutiveact_en.pdf

²⁶ <http://www.dirco.gov.za/au.nepad/nepad.pdf>

²⁷ <https://www.ohchr.org/Documents/Issues/Women/WG/ProtocolontheRightsofWomen.pdf>

²⁸ https://au.int/sites/default/files/treaties/7789-treaty-0033_-_african_youth_charter_e.pdf

²⁹ http://archive.ipu.org/idd-E/afr_charter.pdf

³⁰ <https://www.ifrc.org/docs/IDRL/-%20To%20add/AUCConventionProtectionIDPs2009.pdf>

Local and Global Commitment³¹

State of Human Rights in Africa

Africa has a long history of fissured HR and democratic crises. Certain challenges have historical underpinnings, while others have emerged from inter-state and intra-state disconnections, ideological and political conflicts, disparities, and insufficient dedication to human rights within the African states. Bade (1988, as cited in Falaiye, 2013) underlined that the ultimate roots for Africa’s continuing crises reside in imperialist exploitation of the continent.

HR safeguard in some African states is gradually gripping hold under the HR protection system and regional HR bodies including the constitutions, however, the magnitude of abuses and violations is escalating with time (Amnesty International, 2020; Harris & Vermaak, 2015; Izarali et al., 2019; Magnarella, 2000; Nowrojee, n.d.; Samb, 2009). Falaiye highlights, “Violent conflicts have been a feature of relations among the states from the pre-colonial period to contemporary times” (2013, p.9).

The available reports underlined the abysmal state of HR issues in some parts of Africa, which include but are not limited to the armed conflict and attacks on civilians, forced displacement, domestic violence, racial discrimination, rape, poor health conditions, economic scarcity, lack of access to education, political instability, forced evictions,

³¹ https://ijrcenter.org/courts-monitoring-bodies/#Regional_Human_Rights_Systems

ethnic rivalries, media harassment, denial of various freedoms, and gender-based violence (Amnesty International, 2021a, 2021b; Kevin, 2021; Ordu, 2021a).

Torres (2021) impugned retrogressive interventions and negligence of the states towards socioeconomic rights as the reason behind the recent widespread HR desecrations. There is also a close association between poverty, inactions of the states, and HR violations. It is further exacerbated by structural inequalities, lack of access to social amenities, and food insecurity. In recent times, the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of Africa has significantly grown, with a marked reduction in poverty and inequality in some African nations (African Development Bank Group, 2021a), but it remains the poorest continent with millions of people living under the poverty line³².

To enhance the understanding of the intricate human rights landscape in Africa, the researchers have briefly examined (1) education rights, (2) health rights, and (3) gender equality.

Education rights

Education stands as a pivotal factor in diminishing gender disparities and societal inequities, enhancing job prospects, and promoting participatory democracy and human rights practices (Backhaus & Loichinger, 2021).

Throughout the colonial period, educational accessibility in Africa remained limited, marked by curriculum elements of discrimination and racism. Over time, however, the education system was bolstered through the efforts of local and international leadership and organizations.

The essential right to education is safeguarded by various provisions, including Article 17 of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights; Article 11 of the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child; Article 12 of the Protocol to the African Charter on Human and People's Rights on the Rights of Women in Africa; and Article 13 and 20 of the African Youth Charter. Participation in the Decades of Education (1997-2006 and 2006-2015) constituted a noteworthy endeavor to tackle educational obstacles. African nations are concurrently striving to attain SDGs and fulfill the mandates of the Continental Education Strategy for Africa-CESA 2016–2025 (African Union, 2016). Nevertheless, the current scenario in Africa is characterized by substantial disparities in the realm of education.

In Sub-Saharan Africa, the gross school enrolment ratio is 31% at the pre-primary level; 99.91% at the primary level, (as of 2019)³³ with the completion rate of around 70% (as of 2020)³⁴; 51% at the lower secondary level, and 33% at the upper secondary level. Whereas, the gross enrolment ratio in Northern Africa at the pre-primary level is 41%; 101% at the primary education level; 101% at the lower secondary, and around 63 percent at upper secondary (UNESCO-UIS database, 2021, as cited in UNESCO, 2021). In Sub-Saharan Africa, the literacy rate of people ages 15 and above is 65.5% (as of

³² <https://unctad.org/press-material/facts-and-figures-7>

³³ <https://data.worldbank.org/region/sub-saharan-africa>

³⁴ <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SE.PRM.CMPT.ZS?end=2020&locations=ZG&start=1970&view=chart>

2019)³⁵ with the least educated youth living in Chad (22%) and Mali (31%)³⁶. Whereas, in the Middle East & North Africa, the literacy rate of persons age 15 and above is 90.33%³⁷ (as of 2020). The provided statistics demonstrate a 100% gross enrollment ratio accomplishment at the primary level. However, participation in pre-primary, lower, and upper secondary education, as well as adult literacy, lags behind in Sub-Saharan Africa in comparison to North Africa.

In their study, Evans and Acosta (2021) scrutinized the quality and accessibility of education in Africa, uncovering promising indications such as organized pedagogy, instruction in local languages, school feeding initiatives, removal of fees, and a mixed influence of educational technology.

Over time, strides have been taken to combat illiteracy through increased enrollment ratios. Nonetheless, the sustainability of primary and adult literacy efforts has regressed. Moreover, the quality of education presents a grim outlook. Highlighting the severity of the situation, a report underscored that in 2019, approximately 105 million children of primary and secondary school age in Africa were out of school, accounting for 41 percent of the global total. Furthermore, a significant number of students do not complete their schooling; one in three children within a cohort fails to finish primary education. Moreover, only 41 percent of a cohort completes lower secondary education, and a mere 23 percent successfully completes upper secondary education (UNICEF and the African Union Commission, 2021).

Out-of-school children in Africa, by age group (UNESCO-UIS database, 2021, as cited in UNESCO, 2021)

³⁵ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1233102/adult-literacy-rate-in-sub-saharan-africa/#:~:text=In%202019%2C%2065.5%20percent%20of,was%20measured%20at%2058.9%20percent.>

³⁶ <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SE.ADT.LITR.ZS?locations=ZG>

³⁷ <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SE.ADT.1524.LT.ZS?locations=ZQ>

Gross enrolment ratio (Source: UNESCO-UIS database, 2021, as cited in UNESCO, 2021)

Gender disparity in education remains a major challenge across African countries. Around 52 million girls are out of school³⁸. It is projected that about 9 million will never step into a classroom. The database of UNESCO-UIS (2019, as cited in UNESCO, 2021) further elaborated, “20% of primary-school-age girls are not in school, and the percentage grows dramatically at the upper secondary level where it reaches 60%... In Sub-Saharan Africa, the gender parity index is below one, showing that fewer girls are enrolled across all levels compared to boys. The gender disparity grows at higher levels of education – in Sub-Saharan Africa, only 84 girls to every 100 boys are attending upper secondary schools... On the other hand, more girls are attending upper secondary schools compared to boys in Northern Africa” (p.13).

As indicated by the Women's World Atlas, the majority of African countries are still striving to attain gender parity in tertiary education enrollment. The report underlined, “Women’s education and women’s financial and digital inclusion relative to men are below the world average, with financial inclusion declining over the past four years... Africa’s record is worse than the worldwide average [in violence against women]” (McKinsey Global Institute, 2019)³⁹. While the specific causes of university dropouts remain insufficiently documented, Beyene et al. (2019) highlight the presence of gender-based violence in educational institutions in Sub-Saharan Africa as a significant concern. Ordu (2021b) exposed, “Female faculty and students face sexual harassment, or, at the very least, are too often judged by their physical appearance rather than their intellectual capabilities, which further dissuades them from staying in academia” (p.60).

In recent times, certain regions of Africa have witnessed improvements in their education systems. However, the continent continues to face substantial disparities, an enduring gender gap, and educational discrimination both across and within African nations. Researchers believe that quantitative achievements have been used to mask the education inequities and gender discrimination across the African education system. Overall, there is a huge gap and differences in terms of accessibility, gender parity, and participation in education.

³⁸ <https://www.globalpartnership.org/blog/girls-rights-education-african-traditional-and-religious-leaders-commit-changing-mindsets>

³⁹ For details, check <https://www.womenpoliticalleaders.org/womens-world-atlas-2021/>

Numerous factors have contributed to the troubling condition of education in Africa. Notably, attacks on schools have rendered education inaccessible, especially in regions like West and Central Africa (Human Rights Watch, 2021a, 2021b). UNICEF (2019) underscored that “in Burkina Faso, Cameroon, the Central African Republic, Chad, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, Mali, Niger and Nigeria, a surge in threats and attacks against students, teachers, and schools – on education itself – is casting a foreboding shadow upon children, their families, their communities and society at large”. This is compounded by Musau's findings (2018) which highlight weak economic status, discriminatory social institutions and cultural norms, and poorly resourced education systems as the reason behind education inequalities. Moreover, the feeble governance role, limited budget allocation, insufficient infrastructure, conflict, insecurity, teacher shortages, gender-based violence, and discriminatory practices further impede the African education system.

To plug the gap, understanding the socio-cultural and political situation, the current state of education and policies, the mindset of people and governments towards education, and the availability of resources is crucial.

Health rights

The right to health finds protection within the African Charter, national constitutions, regional regulations, and global treaties. Substantial progress has been achieved in enhancing health outcomes, with notable reductions in child mortality rates, diminishing prevalence of communicable and non-communicable diseases, and enhanced maternal and reproductive health conditions. However, despite these advancements, the African region continues to harbor a fragile healthcare system on the global stage ⁴⁰.

Mortality rate, under-5 (per 1,000 live births) - Sub-Saharan Africa (Source: The World Bank, 2021)⁴¹

⁴⁰ For more information, visit <http://www.africanhealthstats.org/cms/>

⁴¹ <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SH.DYN.MORT?end=2020&locations=ZG&start=1990&view=chart>

Africa has been slow in providing essential healthcare services to women, adolescents, and the elderly. Nearly half of the population in sub-Saharan Africa lacks access to clean water and sanitation services. The available reports confirm the growing number of diseases, high risk of morbidity, malnutrition, and a rise in disability cases across Africa (World Health Organization, 2018a, 2018b). Child mortality remains the highest (around 57 percent) in the world⁴². The continent is further ill-prepared for epidemics and pandemics.

Concerning mental health, the situation is exacerbated. Royal African Society (2020) reported, “Access to mental health care is most challenging for vulnerable populations within [African] countries; including people with low socioeconomic status, women, people residing in rural areas, minority ethnic groups, immigrants and other excluded populations” (p.5).

Economic, political, social, and environmental peculiarities, along with the regionalization of the healthcare responses and outcomes are credited for the underperformance of the health care system in most of the African region. Additionally, obstacles to quality healthcare in Africa encompass poverty, inadequate education, corruption, infrastructure deficits, inadequate healthcare investment, outdated policies and frameworks, and a dearth of skilled medical personnel (Azevedo, 2021). One of the reports exposed, “African health systems are underfunded, overstretched, and understaffed, rendering the challenge of addressing this double disease burden a monumental challenge” (AfDB, 2013). Another report criticized, “Health care access in Africa is heavily dependent on assistance from international donors and aid agencies, along with out-of-pocket payments for services, which places significant strain on low-income households” (Signe, 2021, p.4).

Widespread awareness of health challenges and healthy lifestyles, particularly women empowerment through educational approaches could bridge the conundrum.

Gender Equality

Gender inequalities and gender-based violence are the greatest threats to Africa's development. Back in the pre-colonial period, women enjoyed great respect and honor, but the process of pacification and colonization affected gender systems (Agbaje, 2019; Bertolt, 2018).

Women have been contesting educational, socio-economic, health, and political inequalities for decades. All the colonized policies oppressed women's rights.

The legislative reforms in most of the modern African states guarantee equality and non-discriminatory practices. These states have ratified regional, sub-regional and international instruments including the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW)⁴³, Maputo Protocol⁴⁴, and the African Union Gender Policy⁴⁵.

⁴² <https://data.unicef.org/resources/levels-and-trends-in-child-mortality/>

⁴³ <https://www.ohchr.org/documents/professionalinterest/cedaw.pdf>

⁴⁴ <https://www.ohchr.org/Documents/Issues/Women/WG/ProtocolontheRightsofWomen.pdf>

⁴⁵ https://www.usip.org/sites/default/files/Gender/African_Union_Gender_Policy_2009.pdf

In recent times, there has been marked progress towards gender parity in some African countries like Rwanda. Women's participation in leadership positions has enhanced significantly. Despite, inequality roots that emerged during colonization, continue their hold (AfDB, 2021).

Gender Index Report of 2019 offers an affirmative snapshot of social, economic, educational, and legal development in most of the African countries, but with marked regional gender gaps (African Development Bank and United Nations Economic Commission for Africa, 2020). Patriarchal ideologies, discriminatory laws, segmented labor market, restrictive cultural practices, and persistent gender inequality practices in social institutions, education, and at the workplace have immobilized, and intellectually shattered many women (African Development Bank Group, 2021b; Grantham et al., 2021; World Economic Forum, 2021).

The Africa Gender Index scores (Source: African Development Bank and United Nations Economic Commission for Africa, 2020)

Gender Gap Index (Source: World Economic Forum, Global Gender Gap Index, 2021)⁴⁶

Violence against women is deeply ingrained in social norms. Furthermore, economically empowered women experience heightened levels of violence in Africa (Alesina et al., 2016). According to UNFPA (2021), “The East and Southern Africa region have high rates of sexual violence against women and girls. In seven African countries, around 20 percent of those aged 15 to 24 years reported sexual violence from an intimate partner”. The Social Institutions and Gender Index (SIGI) regional report of Sub-Saharan Africa added, "African women currently face the highest level of discrimination in laws, social norms, and practices compared to women in other regions of the world. Whereas wide variation exists across African countries, the region displays high levels of discrimination in terms of intra-household dynamics and caregiving roles, and the working environment, as well as pervasive and harmful practices including domestic violence and female genital mutilation" (OECD, 2021, p.1).

⁴⁶ <https://www.weforum.org/reports/global-gender-gap-report-2021>

Comparison of Gender inequality at work and in society (Source: McKinsey Global Institute, 2019).

Thus, violence against women persists amid deeply rooted social norms, exacerbated by economic empowerment; regional data highlights high sexual violence rates and pervasive discrimination, underscoring urgent need for change. In short, gender inequality is one of the barriers to tackling poverty in Africa. It has affected educational attainment, healthcare, economic participation, political empowerment, and social life. It is predicted to take more than a hundred years to close the gender gap in the African continent.

Advancing women's equality, fostering economic opportunities, harnessing technology, enforcing women-supportive laws, policies, and regulations, and promoting educational empowerment hold the potential to accelerate gender equity practices, even in times of uncertainty. While the timeline for realizing these advancements remains uncertain, the pursuit of such measures holds the promise of eventual gender equity.

Brief Introduction to Human Rights Education

The concept of HRE aims to instil HR values through education, presenting a comprehensive and meaningful perspective. The entwinement of the right to education and education about HR has led some countries to prioritize the former over the latter.

Within the African context, the concept of HRE draws influence from the UN's definition, yet its effective implementation necessitates adaptation to the local context to avoid being misconstrued.

According to Sadruddin (2019), “HRE is a conscious incessant socio-cognitive and ecoethical learning process that gradually empowers individuals about the rights of self and others. It involves a readiness to make rational and civilized decisions through the conscious filtration of HR ideologies, sociocultural context, and political will. It is a critical component to achieving sustainable development, maintaining human dignity, and applying social justice. It permeates a sense of openness towards embracing multiculturalism, pluralism, and diversity”.

The idea of HRE partly galvanized post-World War II, after the Charter of the United Nations, 1945⁴⁷, and with the inception of UDHR⁴⁸. The significance of education to promote HR is stated in the preamble, Article 19 and 26b of the UDHR, but the declaration is under debate for having political objectives and contingent on ideological filtration. In 1953, UNESCO set up Associated Schools Project Network (ASPnet)⁴⁹. They collaborated with schools around the globe and conducted grassroots pilot projects in favor of learning about the UN System and its role in global concerns such as HR.

Article 7 of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination, 1965⁵⁰; Article 13 of the International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights, 1966⁵¹; and Article 29 of the UN Convention on the Right of the Child, 1989⁵² grounded the purpose of education on the HR principles.

The concept underpinning HRE formally emerged in 1974, when UNESCO placed HRE on the agenda of a General Conference⁵³. In 1978, UNESCO awarded educational institutions, individuals, and organizations who made significant efforts to introduce HRE through teaching and training⁵⁴. In 1993, the International Congress on the education of human rights and democracy, and in the same year, the UNESCO World Conference on Human Rights took place that adopted the Vienna Declaration and Programme of Action⁵⁵. It called for designing an extensive program on HRE to reach a wider population. It states, “The World Conference on Human Rights emphasizes the importance of incorporating the subject of human rights education programs and calls upon States to do so. Education should promote understanding, tolerance, peace and

⁴⁷ <https://treaties.un.org/doc/publication/ctc/uncharter.pdf>

⁴⁸ <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/universal-declaration-of-human-rights>

⁴⁹ For details, see <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000245418>

⁵⁰ <https://www.ohchr.org/en/professionalinterest/pages/cerd.aspx>

⁵¹ <https://www.ohchr.org/en/professionalinterest/pages/cescr.aspx>

⁵² <https://www.ohchr.org/en/professionalinterest/pages/crc.aspx>

⁵³ <https://www.refworld.org/docid/3ae6b390a.html> Also check <https://en.unesco.org/themes/gced/1974recommendation>

⁵⁴ <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000131836>

⁵⁵ <https://www.ohchr.org/en/professionalinterest/pages/vienna.aspx>

friendly relations between the nations and all racial or religious groups and encourage the development of United Nations activities in pursuance of these objectives". To address the shortcomings, i.e., lack of awareness and capacity to promote HRE, the UN General Assembly proclaimed the years 1995-2004 as the UN Decade for Human Rights Education⁵⁶. It called for creating a comprehensive approach to education for HR that can impart knowledge and skills, instil positive values, engage participants in critical dialogues, support democratic participation, and combat gender inequality. During this phase, few regional conferences were held that formulated concrete recommendations to give an impetus to HRE. In 2004, the General Assembly of the United Nations established World Program for HRE⁵⁷ to advance the implementation of HRE plans in all sectors. During the first phase (2005-2009), programs were launched for primary and secondary school systems. In the second phase (2010-2014), the program was expanded to higher education, civil servants, law enforcement officials, and the military. During that stage, some other developments happened. For example, in 2014, Global Coalition for Human Rights Education was formed by NGOs. It emerged as a powerful alliance to support the mission of promoting HRE. In 2011, UNESCO Chair for HRE was established. In the same year, General Assembly adopted the United Nations Declaration on Human Rights Education and Training⁵⁸. Besides, some global universities started offering courses in HRE, which is appreciable. The third phase of the World Program (2015-2019) focused on HR training for media professionals and journalists. Whereas, the fourth phase (2020-2024), concentrates on educating young people about equality, human rights, non-discrimination, inclusion, respect, and diversity⁵⁹. Recently, in 2021, the Berlin Declaration on Education for Sustainable Development committed to base education on HR values⁶⁰, however, local approaches to disseminate HRE are still in discussion.

Researchers strongly criticize the unsustainable approach taken by the World Program that introduced HRE, concentrating on a particular group during each stage, while overlooking the others. Also, HRE is highly influenced by the UN, which is not well-versed, though equipped, to propose HRE in all contexts.

Presently, HRE has gained widespread acceptance and practice in numerous countries. However, the persistent growth of human rights abuses over time raises questions about the effectiveness of HRE in instilling positive values. Researchers critique many developmental stages of HRE as being passive, controlled, and manipulative. Notably, the inclusivity of all countries in decision-making and the absence of comprehensive field studies, especially in developing nations, have hindered a thorough understanding of the

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[https://www.ohchr.org/en/issues/education/training/pages/decade.aspx#:~:text=United%20Nations%20Decade%20for%20Human%20Rights%20Education%20\(1995%2D2004\),-History&text=The%20Conference%20recommended%20that%20States,human%20rights%20and%20fundamental%20freedoms](https://www.ohchr.org/en/issues/education/training/pages/decade.aspx#:~:text=United%20Nations%20Decade%20for%20Human%20Rights%20Education%20(1995%2D2004),-History&text=The%20Conference%20recommended%20that%20States,human%20rights%20and%20fundamental%20freedoms)

⁵⁷

<https://www.ohchr.org/en/issues/education/training/pages/programme.aspx#:~:text=Building%20on%20the%20achievements%20of,strengthen%20partnerships%20and%20cooperation%20from>

⁵⁸ <https://daccess-ods.un.org/tmp/8740224.24221039.html>

⁵⁹

[https://www.ohchr.org/en/issues/education/training/pages/programme.aspx#:~:text=On%2010%20December%202004%2C%20the,113%20\(10%20December%202004\).](https://www.ohchr.org/en/issues/education/training/pages/programme.aspx#:~:text=On%2010%20December%202004%2C%20the,113%20(10%20December%202004).)

⁶⁰ In 2021, the Berlin Declaration on Education for Sustainable Development further committed to base education on human rights values.

existing human rights, education, and HRE landscape, impeding the identification of genuine contextual HRE needs.

In certain instances, Western organizations have exerted influence to implant human rights ideologies based on their own experiences and exposure onto other nations. However, the documents, courses, and models crafted by global experts might prove detrimental within specific sociocultural contexts, given that many of these resources lack localization and thorough critical assessment. While adaptation from the global context is acceptable, it should not undermine or overshadow the significance of the local context.

HRE in Africa

While certain scholars have briefly illuminated the history of HRE in South Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa (Ero, 2013; Mubangizi, 2015; Russell et al., 2019), a comprehensive account of the emergence, approaches, and development of HRE across many African states remains largely uncharted. Where information exists, it reveals variations among African nations, differing across historical, political, socio-economic, cultural, constitutional, and judicial dimensions.

After gaining independence, many African countries joined the UN and followed HR treaties. Ero (2013) narrated, “The UN struggles not only to materialize the rights in the UDHR but also struggles with the foundational task of bringing HRE to poor communities that lack access to such information” (p.117).

HRE discourse gained momentum in Africa through democratic endeavors like constitutions and good governance, yet during the initial stages of decolonization, HR practices failed to permeate informal and formal spheres due to Western influences.

ACHPR was the first regional document that stimulated HRE in Africa. Article 25 reflects on the methodology of HRE and encouraged the states to promote rights through teaching, education, and publication. It highlights, “States parties to the present Charter shall have the duty to promote and ensure through teaching, education and publication, the respect of the rights and freedoms contained in the present Charter and to see to it that these freedoms and rights, as well as corresponding obligations and duties, are understood”.

The UN Decade for Human Rights Education (1995-2004) emerged as an opportunity for Africa to endorse its commitment to HR values. Addo (2000) reflected, “An international strategy for human rights education is an invaluable initiative to policy-making in African states primarily because it complements the continuing efforts to increase levels of literacy among the peoples of Africa but equally significant because such a strategy enhances the efforts to achieve the mutually reinforcing goals of sustainable development, democracy, the rule of law, environmental security and peaceful relations on the continent” (p.96). Initially, only a few African states responded by initiating efforts to advance HRE through school curricula. However, there is limited documentation regarding the government's role in curriculum development, the specific human rights elements incorporated into training programs, and the resulting outcomes of these initiatives.

Subsequently, the launch of the World Program for Human Rights Education occurred, yet numerous African governments did not formulate strategies to promote HRE nor communicated their national HRE endeavors to the UN. Bösl and Jastrzembki (2005, as cited in Horn, 2009) critiqued, “If the major role players – the governments themselves – performed so badly, and if the NGOs, who are praised for their contribution, participated in education only as a secondary interest to boost their main mandates, how can we speak of success at all?” (p.73). We strongly believe that the lack of preparedness of the African government to actively introduce HRE is because of western domination. Yeshanew observed, “The programme under the UN Decade was designed for international application and hence not based specifically on the situation in Africa” (2007, p.192).

The documented role of NGOs, international organizations, and civil society in promoting the right to education contrasts with limited evidence regarding their contributions to HRE programs. For instance, the African Human Rights Project has engaged community-level HRE workers, equipping them with resources to execute numerous HRE micro-projects across over ten countries in East and West Africa (Holland & Martin, 2014). Similarly, Equitas and its partners have provided diverse training through The East Africa Human Rights Program (EAHRP) to enhance the capacities of HR activists, educators, civil society entities, and government agencies in East Africa⁶¹. Similarly, a local NGO initiated the Bons Vizinhas (Good Neighbours) program, delivering HR training to orphans and vulnerable children and youth in Machava Village, Mozambique (Burnett, 2021). In North Africa, Amnesty International has conducted HR training sessions for young human rights educators⁶². Likewise, in collaboration with the Middle East and North Africa (MENA), the Raoul Wallenberg Institute has orchestrated an extensive array of regional training initiatives focused on HR concerns. These programs aim to equip educators, government officials, and civil society representatives with the tools to integrate international HR standards into curricula and enhance teaching methodologies⁶³. Additionally, in partnership with MENA, the Danish Institute for Human Rights has organized capacity-building programs addressing HR matters. These initiatives have fostered HR dialogues by conducting regional HR courses and providing research training for human rights educators and other relevant stakeholders.⁶⁴ Likewise, Equitas has trained more than 250 human rights educators via HRE initiatives and youth-led community projects⁶⁵. In Central Africa, Help Out Centre for Human Rights in Buea, Cameroon, has launched the HRE project⁶⁶. Similarly, Youth for Human Rights International has initiated HRE programs⁶⁷. A few global academic institutions have also contributed their part. For example, in 2016, the Human Rights in Africa class at the Teachers College Columbia University designed the HRE curriculum for the youth and young adults of West Africa with the support of UNESCO and civil society. Then in 2018, they designed a curriculum for the Women’s Institute for Secondary Education and Research (WISER), Kenya. In 2020, they prepared the HRE

⁶¹ <https://equitas.org/where-we-work/east-africa/regional-program/>

⁶² <https://www.amnesty.org/en/latest/education/2016/10/training-young-human-rights-educators-in-the-middle-east-and-north-africa/>

⁶³ <https://rwi.lu.se/where-we-work/regions/middle-east-and-north-africa/>

⁶⁴ <https://www.humanrights.dk/where-we-work/middle-east-north-africa>

⁶⁵ <https://equitas.org/where-we-work/mena/>

⁶⁶ <https://teachingforsolidarity.com/projects/human-rights-education-in-cameroon/>

⁶⁷ <https://www.freedommag.org/issue/201501-religion/world/challenges-human-rights-change-cameroon.html>

curriculum with the support of Haile-Manas Academy and Ethiopia Education Initiatives in Ethiopia⁶⁸.

At the local level, Human Rights organizations like the African Centre for Democracy and Human Rights Studies, South African Human Rights Commission (SAHRC), Arab Network for National Human Rights Institutions (ANNHRI), Network of African National Human Rights Institutions (NANHRI), Africa Foundation for Human Rights and Tolerance, and others have played a role in advancing HRE in Africa. They have contributed through capacity-building programs and policy development. The African Commission, notably, has passed resolutions on HRE, emphasizing the establishment of a legal framework for HRE mechanisms in partnership and collaboration with both state and non-state entities. However, the implementation and outcomes of numerous HRE programs and training by NGOs, international organizations, civil society, and academic institutions have primarily focused on HR advocacy, with limited dissemination of context-specific HRE in Africa. These works are believed to have contributed to passive and hypothetical roles.

In the realm of formal education, the progress of HRE remains a topic of discussion within African education systems. Limited research studies are available, with only a few focusing on the South African perspective (for example, Ahmed et al., 2020; Tibbitts & Keet, 2016). At the school level, certain aspects of HR values are integrated into religious education and social studies textbooks, adapted to diverse contexts. For instance, Russell et al. (2019) scrutinized forty-two South African textbooks, revealing the inclusion of HR discourse within a global and national context across subjects. Notably, life orientation books had the highest concentration of HR references, followed by social studies books, while history contained the fewest mentions. Likewise, a report highlighted the favorable integration of HRE content into primary and secondary school curricula in countries such as Nigeria, Cameroon, Ghana, Ethiopia, and Kenya. Regarding the assessment, HR is included in Ghana's National Pre-Tertiary Learning Assessment Framework⁶⁹. Whereas, in Kenya, provisions to adjust inclusive student assessment practices are mandated (Soomar et al., 2021). The findings reveal the proactive efforts of select African states in incorporating HR elements into school curricula, yet the formal introduction of HRE as a subject remains uncommon in the majority of African schools. In instances where it is available and acknowledged, HRE's presence tends to be limited and lacking in substantive impact.

HRE has experienced a recent surge in popularity at the university level. Several universities have integrated HRE as an interdisciplinary course. Notable examples include the Centre for Human Rights at the University of Pretoria, The African Centre for Democracy and Human Rights Studies in The Gambia, Cairo Institute for Human Rights Studies, Africa University, University of Johannesburg, and University of the Free State. However, the effectiveness and impact of these programs have yet to be fully acknowledged.

⁶⁸ <https://www.tc.columbia.edu/cae/projects/human-rights-education-curricula/#tab-11295869>

⁶⁹ See <https://nacca.gov.gh/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/National-Pre-tertiary-Education-Curriculum-Framework-final.pdf>

In general, the status of HRE in Africa demonstrates progress in certain countries while experiencing setbacks in others. In regions where progress is evident, the quality and sustainability of HRE programs remain uncertain. There is also ambiguity surrounding the contextual alignment of available courses and programs, as their development may be influenced by Western ideologies due to limited exploration. The existing literature suggests that the available courses tend to be conceptually confined, often revolving around UN conventions, declarations, frameworks, and covenants. As stated by Keet (2012) in the South African context, yet applies across the African continent, the HRE field is traditionalist, conceptually confined, conservative, and unproductive. It is inclined to epistemology approach to HR, relying largely on the rational, intellectual mind and less so on a moral and ethical one (Simmond & Preez, 2012)

The literature does not definitively establish whether university learners are motivated to study HR or if they possess a favorable attitude towards addressing global HR issues. Nonetheless, given the exposure to HR violations, there is a presumption that young individuals aspire for opportunities to enhance their understanding and competencies in HR. This drive is likely fueled by a desire to contribute to their own well-being, the advancement of their nation, and the welfare of future generations.

Challenges to Introduce HRE in African Continent

The challenges to introducing HRE in Africa are deeply rooted in structural issues that emerged as a combination of colonization, political, ideological, educational, social, and cultural elements.

Initially, colonization was the barrier to promoting HR values among learners across African states. In the beginning, missionary schools indoctrinated western values and overlooked sociocultural, ethical, and African traditional knowledge. After decolonization, African states inherited a colonial education system that was gradually reoriented to new political and economic tenets (Horn, 2009). The utmost vision of education was to ensure accessibility and to build resilience. However, challenges related to accessibility, quality, and equity intensified over time due to prolonged civil conflicts, financial instability, and insufficient investment in the education sector. Consequently, remnants of colonialism, inadequate infrastructure, and ideological conflicts impeded the progression of democratic values through education.

The present education systems across Africa offer a complex cobweb of HR knowledge. It lacks an action and advocacy approach. André Keet (2007, as cited in Bajaj et al., 2016) stated, “Much of HRE is still “declarationist,” focusing on political literacy or legal compliance but overlooking participatory social change” (p.14). The mystified education systems have been unsuccessful to prevent hate crime, radicalization, and intolerance among young people. Englund (2006) offered a critique of the African curriculum and pedagogical system, highlighting their shortcomings in effectively addressing civic rights and pressing societal issues.

HRE is not on the agenda of teacher education programs across the African states. An exception is the Revised National Curriculum Statement in South Africa that has provided structure and support to mainstream values related to social justice. Teachers lack acquisition of HR literacy, curriculum awareness, and are not adequately trained

about HR teaching methodologies. One of the studies highlighted poor HR knowledge and skills, and a lack of awareness about HR pedagogies among Nigerian teachers because of conservative teacher education programs, strong nationalistic-oriented curriculum, and authoritarian school structures. Also, there is a gap between HR values promoted by the policy makers and the personal values of teachers (Obiagu & Nwaubani, 2020). These factors have embedded reluctance among Nigerian teachers to impart HRE.

African states have demonstrated a lackluster engagement in advancing HRE, evident through their limited involvement in global HRE initiatives like the UN Decade for HRE and the World Programme for Human Rights Education. This hesitancy is partly attributed to the influence of Western dominance. Additionally, the specific roles and responsibilities of states in promoting HRE remain inadequately outlined, possibly stemming from the absence of comprehensive contextual HRE frameworks and policies across the continent. Moreover, HRE has not effectively reached vulnerable populations, educational institutions, and professional groups due to insufficient political commitment and limited support from intergovernmental organizations (Horn, 2009). Researchers suggest that a political disconnect exists within African states, and a comprehensive assessment of HRE needs is yet to be conducted continent-wide.

Maathai (1995, as cited in Dziva et al., 2014) shared that certain African governments persist in exploiting their citizens through neo-colonial practices and political repression, fostering a climate of submission to abuse. In such contexts, the introduction of HRE could potentially empower individuals, leading to increased awareness and potential pressure on the government to address these issues. Maathai described, “African people are still oppressed by their government that is why African governments are against human rights education” (p.204). Cardenas echoed, “The more successful such education is, the greater the risk that government action will be challenged and that the public will make serious demands for compensation and the punishment of human rights abusers” (2005, p.368).

The favorable stance of certain African states towards perpetuating harmful cultural and traditional practices such as Trokosi in Ghana and Togo, Almanjiri practice in Northern Nigeria, female genital mutilation (FGM), breast ironing, early marriage, and virginity testing underscores their apparent indifference towards endorsing Human Rights (HR) values (Glover et al., 2018).

Low literacy and extreme poverty are other possible barriers to introducing HRE. Ero expressed, “Lack of HRE is a difficult problem in [Sub-Saharan] region that has a significant illiterate population, and one which remains increasingly disadvantaged and isolated by the globalizing processes of the world (2013 p.119).

The role of NGOs remains trivial to deliver HRE to wider communities largely because (1) they carry out HR work related to their mandate; (2) they lack coordination with the government. Okafor (2007, as cited in Horn, 2009) expressed, “[Human rights activists] share the life experiences of the governing elite rather than that of marginalized people. Consequently, they are unable to bridge the gap between the elite and the have-nots. While they may understand the needs of the people in terms of human rights, they are not the best people to communicate teach these rights to the marginalized groups” (p.69).

Much of their achievement towards HRE, which in actuality is scanty, is crafted to satisfy funded organizations or to seek public affiliation.

Insufficient knowledge and awareness about HR constitute significant barriers that have hindered African individuals from asserting and practicing their HR. International organizations have struggled to effectively integrate HR knowledge within a local-global context. Horn (2009) narrated, “While it caught up on the ratification of human rights treaties, it failed in teaching the weak, the marginalized, and society at large, but also the powerful judiciary. An African human rights culture and a general knowledge of the rights of all people are still not fully developed, therefore” (pp.60-61). This area has not been much discovered in the African context and needs further exploration.

Continued social inequalities, the absence of a comprehensive HRE policy, and ideological conflicts between African perspectives and Western notions of HRE are additional emerging areas that warrant deeper exploration and attention.

In summary, the obstacles obstructing the introduction of Human Rights Education (HRE) encompass colonization, neo-colonial exploitation, western influence, inadequate infrastructure, limited curricular integration, political inertia, oppression, empowerment apprehensions, low literacy, entrenched harmful practices, inadequate HR awareness, and weak interventions. In-depth field studies are recommended to validate these factors and uncover additional insights across the African continent.

The scoping review reveals the fragility of HR and HRE, attributed to various factors. Insufficient HR empowerment alongside escalating violations, discontent with state policies, repression, marginalization, ideological complexities, cultural vulnerabilities, and insecurities could fuel extremism and violent crime. Contextual HRE emerges as a potential avenue to promote HR values.

Effective HRE is rooted in exposing realities, addressing tangible issues, conveying HR principles and structures, instilling awareness of rights protected by the government, and equipping individuals with skills to apply, share, and mediate HR values amid multifaceted conflicts and challenges. Accordingly, we propose an HRE course founded on the socioecoethical model of HRE.

About Socioecoethical Model of Human Rights Education (MSEEM)⁷⁰

MSEEM is the culmination of a decade-long effort to document and observe HRE practices in various teaching and learning environments. Using grounded theory, the author gathered HRE perspectives from learners and practitioners in over 47 developing and developed countries via netnography, resulting in the emergence of MSEEM.

MSEEM has taken an integrative, dialectical, and utilitarian approach to introduce HRE to teachers, educators, learners, and anyone, who wishes to disseminate HR values to wider communities through the lens of social consciousness. It applies to all levels and types of education, in both developed and developing countries (Sadruddin, 2019).

⁷⁰ https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3755005

This tripartite model [möbius strip] conjoins social, ecological, and ethrical elements that interact dialectically for building resilience and supporting HRE practices. Recognizing the importance of sociocultural structures and self-actualization is crucial to embracing and practicing common social rights. Similarly, developing an ecological identity narrative offers insights into personal identity and relationships with social, cultural, political, and economic environments. Ethics, in this context, is an individual pursuit of critical selfdiscovery. While personal values evolve through experience and exposure, they are often rooted in social and relational identities. It demands individuals take ownership and filter them through the personal and collective lens. In Sadruddin's viewpoint, HRE is situated in context.

Existing HRE practices must be revamped with an integration of socioecoethical concepts into HRE curricula followed by glocalize knowledge and skills, to develop a deeper understanding of how human rights are interconnected and are essential for creating a just and sustainable world.

As formal and non-formal education opportunities are not universally accessible to all due to escalated educational poverty, the informal method must also be taken on board to infuse human rights values. According to Munir, "We need to dismantle the social construct that regards HRE as an elite subject for the privileged, by blurring the boundaries to its dissemination".

Many people are aware of the fragility of their rights and are often subject to discrimination, hindering their ability to learn and understand HR practices and take civilized actions. Failing to accommodate human rights education in informal educational settings risks leaving young minds, adults, individuals belonging to marginalized communities, and elderly people susceptible to violence. Therefore, it is essential to incorporate informal human rights education to promote positive human rights values that are culturally appropriate and inclusive.

Phases

In certain regions, specific factors may discourage policymakers from promoting human rights values. Moreover, many developing and underdeveloped nations oppose Western human rights laws and values, perceiving them as a potential threat to their cultural value systems. Therefore, the journey of HRE should begin with an assessment of the sociocultural context and political will- examining the socio-political and ideological practices of a country, the state of human rights, and cultural perspectives on human rights values.

Next, it is important to assess the dynamism of the ecological environment, including the convergence (social acceptance) and divergence (sensitivities) of human rights, the risks and opportunities of teaching human rights, and the policies and practices related to human rights education at multiple levels. This includes evaluating the state of human rights education (curriculum, courses, units, training module- direct and indirect) and its impact on an individual's well-being, the community, and the policy-making process.

During the ethrical stage, individuals are expected to actively engage in the process of ethical decision-making through the application of critical thinking skills. Ecological

identity exploration is crucial to facilitate this process. This involves examining one's relationship with the surroundings and understanding the impact of one's actions on the world around them. By exploring ecological identity, individuals can develop a greater sense of responsibility and accountability for their actions and decisions. This, in turn, helps to promote a more ethical and sustainable approach to decision-making in HRE.

In the fourth phase, a combination of cyber ethnography, netnography, and field study can be employed to assess an individual's general understanding, attitudes, and preferred areas of human rights learning.

Sadrudin argues that human rights educators often extract or adapt the best practices or models of human rights curricula from other countries, which may not adequately address the specific needs of a particular country. This approach can lead to the setting of lofty goals and the creation of momentum within the bureaucracy, which may fail to address context-based issues.

After initial filtration, decisions about the content of HRE should be made with consideration of the local context. The course should begin by discussing fundamental concepts, such as basic rights, human rights values, and movements, particularly in the local context. When discussing HR laws and policies, HRE movements, and their existing state, local complexities, and opportunities should be considered. The course must then include filtered global human rights values to help learners recognize the interconnectedness of human rights issues around the world and appreciate the diversity of cultures and experiences. This approach will provide learners with contextual understanding and relevance, increasing their likelihood of actively engaging in informed and constructive actions that can bring about positive change.

To ensure a comprehensive and culturally relevant approach to HRE, it is crucial to gather and filter pertinent resources (both formal and informal). A recommended approach is to prioritize the collection of local knowledge and then filter and supplement it with suitable global human rights content that aligns with the sociocultural context of the country. While the adaptation of resources may be necessary, they must remain socio-culturally appropriate. To this end, the development of localized open educational resources is necessary to promote sustainable open educational practices in HRE.

Essential competencies and skills empowerment such as critical thinking, decision-making, situation analysis, social and voluntary skills, digital literacy, counseling skills, mental health well-being, peacebuilding, and negotiation, green education, peace leadership, and environmental literacy must be negotiated within and beyond the cultural context. Heutagogy, peeragogy, and case-study-based approaches are three potential teaching strategies that can be effective in various contexts.

Finally, teaching HRE alone does not ensure peace and unity in the world. The actual litmus test is reflected through attitudes and actions in a sustainable way, and that is challenging to evaluate.

Munir asserts that the absence of familial or social identity can exacerbate grievances, which may further escalate when individuals lack the skills to manage internal conflicts. In such cases, it is vital to build resilience.

Munir's socioecoethical model of human rights education focuses on empowering individuals about human rights rationally and contextually. By adopting this model, there is a potential to foster a more inclusive society.

Dr. Munir pioneered 'loglocal' approach to teaching HRE. This approach aims to promote a deeper understanding and appreciation of HRE by first building on learners' existing knowledge and experiences of their local cultures, societies, policies, and practices. This is done to ensure that the content being taught is relevant and meaningful. Once learners develop a strong understanding of HR in local context, the loglocal approach then introduces them to global knowledge and perspectives on HR. This helps to broaden their perspectives of HRE through the lens of multicultural and social contexts. The loglocal approach also emphasizes the importance of adapting global content to local contexts. This is done by encouraging learners to critically examine global perspectives and to identify ways in which they can be applied to their communities. This ensures that the content being taught is not only relevant but also culturally sensitive and respectful.

Thus, Munir's socioecoethical model of HRE has the potential to build an inclusive society by empowering people about HR, rationally and contextually.

Researchers elucidate that emphasizing HRE converging to African traditional and contextual knowledge does not entirely mean infusing ideological knowledge rather filtering both local and global content, to avoid drainage outcomes.

Recommendations and Way Forward

- Sensitize policy makers
- Entrench HRE at all levels in the academia regardless of disciplines.
- Introduce contextual HRE curricula based on socioecoethical model
- Consider sociocultural and political constraints while designing curricula
- Teaching sensitive topics through appropriate methodologies
- Design Open Educational Resources on HRE in Africa, and develop a repository of HRE resources, suitable to African context
- Draft HRE policy for Africa
- Pilot the drafted course

Course Outline

Unit 1: Introduction to Human Rights

Learning Objective

- Understand conceptual and philosophical foundations of human rights
- Recognize the key influences that have shaped human rights
- Deepen knowledge about the origin and the evolution of human rights
- Discuss fundamental elements of HR
- Explore and critically assess human rights generations and the changing dichotomies

Topics

- Fundamental Concepts of Rights and Human Rights in African Context
- Sources of Human Rights
- Origin of Human Rights
 - The Cyrus Cylinder
 - The Magna Carta
 - The Petition of Right
 - The English Bill of Rights
 - Declaration of the Rights of the Man and of the Citizen, 1789
 - The First Geneva Convention
- Human Rights in the Contemporary World
- Evolution of Human Rights in Africa- Struggle Movement
 - Pre-colonial, colonial, post-colonial, and contemporary eras
 - African nationalism and pan-Africanism
 - Constitutional Provisions
 - African Socialism
- Generations of Human Rights
 - Civil and Political Rights
 - Social, Economic, and Cultural Rights
 - Solidarity Rights
- Changing Dichotomies

Proposed Digital Resources

Bankie, B.F., & Mchombu, K. (2008). *Pan-Africanism/African Nationalism-Strengthening the unity of Africa and its Diaspora*. The Red Sea Press, Inc.

<https://isejarah.fib.unair.ac.id/wp-content/uploads/2017/09/PAN-AFRICA-AFRICA-NATIONALISM.compressed.pdf>

Declaration of the Rights of the Man and of the Citizen, 1789:

https://constitutionnet.org/sites/default/files/declaration_of_the_rights_of_man_1789.pdf

- Domaradzki, S., Khvostova, M. & Pupovac, D. (2019). Karel Vasak's generations of rights and the contemporary human rights discourse. *Human Rights Review*, 20, 423-443. <https://link.springer.com/content/pdf/10.1007/s12142-019-00565-x.pdf>
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- The Cyrus Cylinder: https://www.guerrillascholar.com/library/The_Cyrus_Cylinder.pdf
- The English Bill of Rights: <https://www.ssc.wisc.edu/~rkeyser/wp/wp-content/uploads/2015/06/English-Bill-of-Rights1.pdf>
- The Magna Carta: <https://liberalarts.utexas.edu/coretexts/files/resources/texts/c/1215%20Magna%20Carta.pdf>
- The Petition of Rights: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/aep/Cha1/3/1/data.pdf>

Books

- An-naim, A.A., & Deng, F.M. (2010). *Human rights in Africa: Cross-cultural perspectives*. Brookings Institution Press.
- Coundouriotis, E. (2020). *Narrating human rights in Africa*. Taylor & Francis Group.
- Heyns, C.H., & Stefiszyn, K. (2006). *Human rights, peace and justice in Africa: A Reader*. PULP.
- Ibhawoh, B. (2018). *Human rights in Africa*. Cambridge University Press.

Unit 2: Overview on the State of Human Rights in African Continent

Learning Objective

- Explore and critically analyse the human rights condition in the African continent
- Discuss, understand, and examine the contemporary HR trends and issues across Africa

Topics

- The State of Human Rights in African Continent
 - Children Rights
 - Gender and Women Rights
 - Elderly Persons Rights
 - Persons with Disabilities Rights
 - Indigenous People Rights
 - Minorities Rights
- Human Rights Trends and Issues
 - Harmful Traditional Practices
 - Democracy and Security Challenges
 - Socio-Cultural Challenges
 - Refugees Crises
 - Freedom Struggles
 - Discrimination and Marginalization
 - Gender-based Violence
 - Environment and Climate Change Issues

Proposed Digital Resources

Amoo, E.O., Olawole-Issac, A., Ajayi, M.P., Adekeye, O., Ogundipe, O., & Olawande, O. (2019). Are there traditional practices that affect men's reproductive health in sub-Saharan Africa? A systematic review and meta-analysis approach. *Cogent Social Sciences*, 5(1), 1677120,

<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.1080/23311886.2019.1677120?needAccess=true>

Anon. (2019). *Harmful social, cultural or religious practices*.

[http://www.lac.org.na/projects/grap/Pdf/20-](http://www.lac.org.na/projects/grap/Pdf/20-Harmful%20Social%20Cultural%20or%20Religious%20Practices.pdf)

[Harmful Social Cultural or Religious Practices.pdf](http://www.lac.org.na/projects/grap/Pdf/20-Harmful%20Social%20Cultural%20or%20Religious%20Practices.pdf)

Austin. (2015, April 29). *Children's rights in Africa* [blog].

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Beyene, A.S., Chojenta, C., Roba, H.S., Melka, A.S., & Loxton, D. (2019). Gender-based violence among female youths in educational institutions of Sub-Saharan Africa: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Systematic Reviews*, 8, 59,

<https://systematicreviewsjournal.biomedcentral.com/track/pdf/10.1186/s13643-019-0969-9.pdf>

Glover, J., Liebling, H., Goodman, S., & Barrett, H. (2018). Persistence and resistance of harmful traditional practices (HTPs) perpetuated against girls in Africa and Asia. *Journal of International Women's Studies*, 19(2), 44-64.

<https://vc.bridgew.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?referer=&httpsredir=1&article=2003&context=jiws>

United Nations Human Rights. (2012). *Human rights indicators- A guide to measurement and implementation*. United Nations.

https://www.ohchr.org/Documents/Publications/Human_rights_indicators_en.pdf

United Nations Human Rights. *Universal Human Rights Index (UHRI)*.

<https://uhri.ohchr.org/en/>

Books

Izarali, M.R., Masakure, O., & Ibhawoh, B. (2019). *Expanding perspectives on human rights in Africa*. Taylor & Francis.

Sahle, E.N. (2019). *Human rights in Africa: Contemporary debates and struggles*. Springer.

Bruey, V.F. (2021). *Patriarchy and gender in Africa*. Rowman & Littlefield.

Coundouriotis, E. (2020). *Narrating human rights in Africa*. Taylor & Francis Group.

Unit 3: International and Regional Laws and Policies about Human Rights

Learning Objective

- Understand the characteristics and complexities of human rights documents
- Discuss and compare the contribution of global and regional human rights policies and laws
- Understand the legacy of African dignitaries, and contribution of regional human rights bodies in establishing HR systems in Africa

Topics

- Global
 - Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 1948 (UDHR)
 - The Cairo Declaration on Human Rights, 1990
 - Sustainable Development Goals and Human Rights
- Regional
 - The African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights
 - The African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child
 - Protocol on the Rights of Women in Africa (Maputo Protocol)
 - Draft Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities in Africa
 - African Youth Charter
 - African Charter on Democracy, Elections, and Governance
 - African Union Convention for the Protection and Assistance of Internally Displaced Persons
 - African Union Gender Policy
- African Leaders and Human Rights Struggles
 - Nelson Mandela, Kofi Annan, Kwame Nkrumah, Ellen Johnson Sirleaf
- Organizations and Regional Human Rights Bodies
 - Organization of African Unity (OAU)
 - African Union (AU)
 - African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights
 - African Court on Human Peoples' Rights (AfCHPR)

Proposed Digital Resources

African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights: <https://www.achpr.org/>

African Court on Human Peoples' Rights (AfCHPR): <https://www.achpr.org/afchpr/>

African Union. (2005). *Protocol on the Rights of Women in Africa (Maputo Protocol)*.

<https://www.ohchr.org/Documents/Issues/Women/WG/ProtocolontheRightsofWomen.pdf>

African Union. (2006). *African Youth Charter*.

<https://au.int/sites/default/files/treaties/7789-treaty-0033 - african youth charter e.pdf>

African Union. (2009). *African Union Convention for the Protection and Assistance of Internally Displaced Persons*. <https://www.unhcr.org/uk/50f9551f9.pdf>

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African Union (OAU): <https://au.int/en/overview>
https://au.int/sites/default/files/treaties/36390-treaty-0011_-_african_charter_on_human_and_peoples_rights_e.pdf

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Organization of African Unity. (1990). *African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child*. https://www.achpr.org/public/Document/file/English/achpr_instr_charterchild_eng.pdf

Organization of African Unity. (2003). *African Charter on Democracy, Elections, and Governance*. http://archive.ipu.org/idd-E/afr_charter.pdf

Organization of Islamic Cooperation. (1990). *The Cairo Declaration of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation on Human Rights*. https://www.oic-oci.org/upload/pages/conventions/en/CDHRI_2021_ENG.pdf

United Nations Human Rights. (n.d.). *Sustainable Development Goals Related human rights*. https://www.ohchr.org/Documents/Issues/MDGs/Post2015/SDG_HR_Table.pdf

United Nations. (1949). *United Nations Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1948*. <https://www.jus.uio.no/lm/en/pdf/un.universal.declaration.of.human.rights.1948.portrait.letter.pdf>

United Nations. (2015). *Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR)*. https://www.un.org/en/udhrbook/pdf/udhr_booklet_en_web.pdf

Books

Eze, C. (2021). *Justice and human rights in the African imagination: We, too, are humans*. Taylor & Francis.

Pretoria University Law Press. (2016). *A guide to the African human rights system*. <https://www.corteidh.or.cr/tablas/31712.pdf>

Unit 4: Introduction to Human Rights Education

Learning Objective

- Understand the relationship between right to education, human rights, and human rights education
- Understand HRE movements
- Examine state and need of HRE in Africa

Topics

- Defining Human Rights Education
 - Human Rights Education
 - Goals of Human Rights Education
 - Principles of HRE
 - Significance and Scope of HRE
- Evolution of Human Rights Education
 - UNESCO Associated Schools Program (Associated Schools Project Network (ASPnet))
 - The World Conference on Human Rights
 - The UN Decade of Human Rights Education (1995-2004)
 - World Program for Human Rights Education (First phase- primary and secondary school systems, 2005–2009); (Second phase- higher education, civil servants, law enforcement officials and the military, 2010–2014); (Third phase- HR training for media professionals and journalists, 2015-2019); (Fourth phase- educating young people about equality, human rights, non-discrimination, inclusion, respect, and diversity, 2020-2024)
 - United Nations Declaration on Human Rights Education and Training
- Human Rights Education in Africa
 - Development, Challenges, Complexities, Opportunities, and Needs
 - Human rights-based approach to Education for All

Proposed Digital Resources

Horn, N. (n.d.). *Human rights education in Africa*.

https://www.kas.de/c/document_library/get_file?uuid=a772df28-cfc4-4205-8004-8268ff2bb18b&groupId=252038

OHCHR. (1993). *Vienna Declaration and Programme of Action*.

<https://www.ohchr.org/Documents/ProfessionalInterest/vienna.pdf>

UNESDOC. (2016). *Evaluation of the UNESCO Associated Schools Project Network (ASPnet)*. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000245418>

United Nations Decade for Human Rights Education (1995-2004):

<https://www.ohchr.org/EN/Issues/Education/Training/Pages/Decade.aspx>

United Nations Declaration on Human Rights Education and Training:

<https://www.ohchr.org/en/issues/education/training/pages/undhreducationtraining.aspx>

World Programme for Human Rights Education:

[https://www.ohchr.org/en/issues/education/training/pages/programme.aspx#:~:text=On%2010%20December%202004%2C%20the,113%20\(10%20December%202004\)](https://www.ohchr.org/en/issues/education/training/pages/programme.aspx#:~:text=On%2010%20December%202004%2C%20the,113%20(10%20December%202004))

Books

Coysh, J. (2017). *Human rights education and the politics of knowledge*. Taylor & Francis.

Manthalu, C.H., Chikaipa, V., & Gunde, A.M. (2021). *Education, communication and democracy in Africa: A democratic pedagogy for the future*. Taylor & Francis.

Zembylas, M., & Keet, A. (2019). *Critical human rights education: Advancing social-justice-oriented educational praxes*. Springer Nature.

Unit 5: HRE as a field of educational practice

Learning Objective

- Examine the relationship between HRE and other fields of study
- Provide a general understanding of HRE policies and practices
- Become familiar with HRE models and its application
- Discuss the role of HRE to address inequalities and discriminatory practices, and advance justice

Topics

- Brief Introduction to the Thematic Study
 - Peace Education
 - Multicultural Education
 - Environmental Education
 - Citizenship Education
 - Inclusive Education
- Human Rights Education Framework
 - Conceptualizing Standards on HRE
 - Policies and Practices of HRE
- The Human Rights Education Models
 - Value and Awareness Model
 - Accountability Model
 - Transformational Model
 - Socioecoethical Model
- Role of HRE to address inequalities and discriminatory practices

Proposed Digital Resources

Akkari, A., & Maleq, K. (2020). *Global citizenship education: Critical and international perspectives*. Springer Nature.

Banks, J.A. (2014). *An introduction to multicultural education* (5th Edition). Pearson.

<https://ucarecdn.com/985ec348-1b3e-4098-bcb7-5d95e616615c/>

Human Rights Education Models: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Human_rights_education

Navarro-Castro, L., & Nario-Galace, J. (2010). *Peace education- A pathway to a culture of peace* (2nd Edition) Center for Peace Education.

https://www.mc.edu.ph/Portals/8/Resources/Peace_Education_ebook_2010.pdf

Books

Otiende, J.E. (2008). *Introduction to environmental education*. University of Nairobi Press.

Unit 6: HRE Skills Empowerment

Learning Objective

Essential competencies and skills empowerment to exercise equality, dignity, and respect
Skills application to propose solutions to the local HR issues in family and public spheres

Topics

- Skills Empowerment
 - Social and Emotional Skills
 - Conflict Management
 - Negotiation Skills
 - Counseling Skills
 - Problem Solving Skills
 - Leadership Skills
 - Communication Skills
 - Ethical Thinking
 - Intercultural Skills
 - Advocacy through Writing
 - Introduction to Research in Human Rights
 - Fundraising Skills
 - Becoming a Member of a Civil Society Organization

Books

Andreassen, B.A., Sano, H., & McInerney-Lankford, S. (2017). *Research methods in education: A handbook*. Edward Elgar Publishing.

McConnell, L., & Smith, R. (2018). *Research methods in human rights*. Routledge.

Unit 6: Case Studies

Learning Objective

Enable participants to apply skills and take a critical approach to reconcile human rights challenges

Topics

- Skills Empowerment
 - Case Studies about Human Rights

Proposed Heutagogical Approaches

- Socioecoehtical approach
- Participatory, Open-ended, and Experiential Learning
- Transformative Learning Model
- Case Studies
- Community Work
- Vicarious and Rhizomatic Learning
- Field Ethnography
- Reflective Narratives
- Situation Analysis
- Documentaries
- Moot/ Mock Trials
- Role Play
- Field Trips
- Group Discussion
- Research Writing
- Storytelling
- Simulations

Note: There is a plethora of global content, but the resources in the local context are sparse. A good number of proposed resources needs filtration. It is therefore suggested to conduct a pilot study of this course with university learners under a human-centred design approach. For filtration of resources, searching for contextual videos and other materials, and translating the available documents into regional language, it is proposed to engage participants into communities of practices. An online repository of contextual resources must be established. It is also suggested to design an open educational learning and teaching manual on HRE in the African context.

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Appendices

As a Virtual Fellow, I contributed the following:

- Attended Public Lecture on Supranaturality, Supernaturality and Spirituality in the Yoruba World by Professor Toyin Falola, January 10, 2022
- Attended Documentary Screening African Concept of Development and Fattening Room, and Book Launch The Little Book of African Development Perspectives, December 8, 2021.
- Attended Guest Lecture titled Revisiting "Tin-Trunk" Literacy in Africa: The Value of Internal Sources for Knowledge Production by Professor Dr. Olufunke Adeboye, Feb 16, 2022.
- Participated as a Cluster Member and Research Fellow in a lecture titled Trans-Sociological Hybridity: Conceptualizing African Contemporary Dance Identity by Dr. Oluwatoyin Olakodana-James, University of Lagos, May 2021
- Delivered lecture on the topic titled 'Brief Overview on The State of Human Rights Education (HRE), and Challenges of Introducing HRE in Africa- Hanking Conundrum' on 15 March 2022

Presentation Copy

**Brief Overview on the State of Human Rights Education (HRE), and Challenges of Introducing HRE in Africa-
Hankering Conundrum**

Dr. Munir Moosa Sadruddin

Mentor, Professor Dr. Muyiwa Falaiye

Format

- HRE in Africa
- Challenges to Introduce HRE in African Continent

Normal is an illusion. What is normal for the spider is chaos for the fly-
Morticia Addams

Human Rights Education

- Conscious incessant socio-cognitive and eco-ethical learning process
- Preparedness toward taking rational decisions through the conscious filtration of HR ideologies, sociocultural context, and political will

4

Timeline

5

Struggles
Complexities
Vulnerabilities

“Violent conflicts have been a feature of relations among the states from the pre-colonial period to contemporary times” (Falaiye, 2013, p.9).

6

HRE in Africa

7

- The state of HRE is progressive in a few and regressive in other African countries.
- The available courses are conceptually imprisoned, dominated by the UN conventions, declarations, frameworks, and covenants.

8

Challenges to Introduce HRE in African Continent

9

- “African people are still oppressed by their government that is why African governments are against human rights education” (Maathai, p.204).
- “The more successful such education is, the greater the risk that government action will be challenged and that the public will make serious demands for compensation and the punishment of human rights abusers” (Cardenas, 2005, p.368).

10

Challenges to Introduce HRE in African Continent

Inhumane Cultural and Traditional Practices

Low Literacy and Extreme Poverty

Role of NGOs

Lack of Adequate Knowledge and Awareness

11

- “While it caught up on the ratification of human rights treaties, it failed in teaching the weak, the marginalized, and society at large, but also the powerful judiciary. An African human rights culture and a general knowledge of the rights of all people are still not fully developed, therefore” (Horn, 2009, pp.60-61).

12

- Persistent social inequalities, lack of comprehensive HRE policy, and HRE ideological clashes between Africa and the west.

13

Fragile HR and HRE

14

15

Suggestions

- Sensitization of policy makers
- Entrenched HRE at all levels in the academia regardless of disciplines.
- From local to global
- Consider sociocultural and political constraints while designing curricula
- Teaching sensitive topics through appropriate methodologies

16

Future Prospects

- Design OER on HRE in Africa and develop a repository of HRE resources
- Draft HRE policy for Africa
- Promote Socioecoethical model
- Pilot this course

17

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Prof. Muyiwa Falaiye, Ph.D., MNAL

Academic Co-Ordinator

Ayo Yusuff, Ph.D.

5 April, 2022

To: Prof. Dr. Munir Moosa Sadruddin
B2 Fatima Square, 418/1 Shivratan Street
Garden East, Karachi-74550.

Re: LAGOS AFRICAN CLUSTER CENTRE: FELLOWSHIP PROGRAM 2020-21

Completion of Fellowship

Prof. Dr. Munir Moosa Sadruddin was awarded the Fellowship of the University of Lagos African Cluster Centre for the year 2021.

Owing to the COVID-19 Pandemic of the same year, Dr. Sadruddin was unable to take up the fellowship position in-person. In 2022, the Fellowship was converted to a Virtual one, starting from 2 January until 1 April, 2022.

Upon the fulfilment of the conditions and requirements for the Fellowship awarded by the Lagos African Cluster Centre (LACC) Africa Multiple Cluster of Excellence, which included a joint research project with his Host Scholar Prof. Dr. Muiyiwa Falaiye, teaching and Curriculum development for the M.A African Studies Programme and the presentation of a Cluster-wide lecture; it is gratifying to note that Dr. Sadruddin's time as a Fellow was rewarding and engaging for both the IADS and Lagos ACC.

We are happy Dr. Sadruddin acquitted himself excellently.

Respectfully,

Prof Muiyiwa Falaiye, Ph.D, MNAL

